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Downscaling climate impacts and decarbonisation pathways in EU Islands, and enhancing socioeconomic and non-market evaluation of Climate Change for Europe, for 2050 and beyond

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Work Package 4: Modelling Climate impacts in 11 EU islands' case studies for 2030- 2100

Deliverable 4.2. High resolution wave and sea level climatology atlas

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1. Introduction

Coastlines are vulnerable to the combined climate change-induced effects of sea level rise and of an enhanced frequency of storm-generated extreme waves, which together concur to determine coastal flooding and coastal erosion, and negatively affect the coastal environment and maritime economic activities.

Assessment of coastal risks due to climate change have tended to focus on the impacts of sea level rise [Nicholls et al., 2011], while few studies investigated the relative contribution of waves and surges to the overall magnitude of the projected extreme events, or their role in causing extreme coastal erosion and flooding, independent of sea level rise [Masselink et al., 2016; Barnard et al., 2015].

On the other hand, ocean wave and surge forecast and hindcast have traditionally been of huge significance for the construction and operation of offshore installations, for the design of port and harbour structures and for the management of naval operations, but only recently the necessity has been widely recognized of incorporating the effects of climate change and of long-term variability into engineering design [Santo et al., 2016]

A first global-scale analysis of the main drivers of coastal flooding due to large-scale oceanographic factors has been recently presented for the first time, relying on a computer-based identification of geographical areas with homogeneous climates [Rueda et al., 2017]. Coastal flood hazard climates were classified as a function of the joint influence of astronomical tides, storm surges, and wave-induced elevated water levels, providing a consistent methodology for understanding the mechanisms of coastal flood hazard on a global scale and guidance for future assessments. However, due to the generally low resolution of available data at the global scale, both the Mediterranean and the Baltic Sea are missing in the analysis, and European costs and islands still lack a coherent and comprehensive impact-oriented treatment of the driving factors of coastal hazards. This is not surprising, as climate change impacts are usually dealt with from a local perspective, and, while there is an ever increasing number of studies dedicated to specific segments of the European coastline, little effort has been dedicated to ensuring overall consistency and comparability of results at the continental scale [Wolff et al., 2018].

Here we review the wave and surge data sources selected for SOCLIMPACT, mainly focusing on the Atlantic Ocean and the Mediterranean Sea and derived from recent simulations (Conte and Lionello, 2013, Lionello et al. 2017). The characteristics of the derived climatology will be presented, aiming to produce a coherent picture of climate-induced changes in the magnitude and distribution of surge and wave

characteristics and their contribution to sea level, to assess data gaps and guide the subsequent computation of hazard indexes to be presented in D4.3 and D4.4b.

The data collected and produced within SOCLIMPACT will be made available to end-users through a dedicated webpage, under sharing policy and standards to be agreed among partners.

2. Review of observations available over the areas of interest for SOCLIMPACT

2.1 Data sources and characteristics

In-situ wave observations for the Global Ocean and the Mediterranean Sea are available through the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service, either near-real-time (from 2010 to present) or delayed (from 1990 to 2016). The former are designed for assimilation into operational models operated by ocean forecasting centres and are collected from main global networks (Argo, GOSUD, Oceansites, GTS), completed by European data provided by EUROGOOS regional systems and national data providers, assembled by the In-Situ TAC regional components. The data are quality controlled using automated procedures and assessed using statistical analysis residuals. The dataset is continuously updated and provides observations with 24-48 hours from acquisition in average.

On the other hand, delayed data integrate wave observations aggregated and validated from the Regional EuroGOOS consortium (Arctic-ROOS, BOOS, NOOS, IBI-ROOS, MONGOOS) and Black Sea GOOS as well as from National Data Centers (NODCs) and JCOMM global systems (Argo, GOSUD, OceanSITES, GTSP, DBCP) and the Global telecommunication system (GTS) used by the Met Offices.

Both data types carry with them the inherent limitations of in-situ data, and often only cover limited areas or selected locations.

Mono-mission satellite-based along-track significant wave height sparse data (from altimetry) are also made available through Copernicus, on a reference grid of 7km x 7km resolution, from 2017-07-09 to present, with a 3-hourly temporal update. Global real time wave data from Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) provide significant swell height, peak period and peak direction, with a daily temporal resolution. Although the spatial coverage of satellite data is indeed more useful for climatological applications, the time period covered does not allow their use for the validation of climate simulations. The same consideration holds for reanalysis products, which date back to 2016/2017 for the areas covered by SOCLIMPACT.

The lack of long-term wave records based on in situ measurements and surge archives

prevents the development of a 20th century climatology for waves and storm surges that is purely observational and recommends the use of numerical models to reconstruct wave and storm surge climatology [Muis et al., 2016]. Several weather forecast centres produce these global atmospheric re-analyses, including the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF).

2.2 Data analysis

Given the insufficient time coverage of satellite data and new generation model analyses, the only capable of providing a distributed (gridded) high-resolution representation of wave fields, it is not possible to perform consistent climatological analyses of wave climatology for the areas of interest. On the other hand, less recent analyses (Cox and Swail, 2001; Swail and Cox, 2001; ERA-40; C-ERA40) have very low spatial resolutions and have anyway been already thoroughly analyzed (Caires et al., 2004a; Caires et al., 2004b; Caires and Sterl, 2005; Semedo et al. 2011, among others). Monthly, annual and decadal statistics based on ERA-40 and C-ERA40 have been synthesized in a global wave climatology atlas available at <http://www.knmi.nl/waveatlas>, which gives a complete picture of the global wave climate and variability. However, although these datasets certainly represent an invaluable large-scale resource and benchmark, they can hardly be exhaustive for local impact studies.

In the following only in-situ data will be used, where available, for a preliminary analysis of model validation.

3. Review of model data available over the areas of interest for SOCLIMPACT

3.1 Input data sources

Atmospheric input data to drive wave and surge models have been produced by a variety of international programmes and projects. Here we list those used for SOCLIMPACT.

3.1.1 Global simulations

An ensemble of wave simulations for the global ocean has been produced with the wave model WaveWatchIII, driven by surface winds derived from 8 different CMIP5 GCM models (see Table 1 below).

Table 1: global forcing models used for wave simulations

DRIVING MODEL	FULL MODEL NAME	ATM RESOLUTION LON X LAT
ACCESS1.0	AustralianCommunityClimateandEarthSystemSimulator1.0	1.88°x1.25°
BCC-CSM1.1	BeijingClimateCentre,ClimateSystemModel,1-1	2.8°x2.8°
CNRM-CM5	CentreNationaldeRecherchesMeteorologiquesCoupledGlobalClimateModel,version5	1.4°x1.4°
MRI-CGCM3	MeteorologicalResearchInstituteCoupledAtmosphere-OceanGeneralCirculationModel,version3	1.1°x1.1°
MIROC5	ModelforInterdisciplinaryResearchonClimate,version5	1.4°x1.4°
INMCM4	InstituteofNumericalMathematicsCoupledModel,version4.0	2.0°x1.5°
HadGEM2-ES	HadleyCentreGlobalEnvironmentalModel2,EarthSystem	1.88°x1.25°
GFDL-ESM2M	GeophysicalFluidDynamicsLaboratoryEarthSystemModel2M	2.5°x2.0°

3.1.2 Regional simulations

Driving simulations for the CMCC Mediterranean wave model

For the Mediterranean basin, an ensemble of simulations has been performed by CMCC using wind surface fields from two different European Projects as forcing:

- **CIRCE** (Climate change and impact research: the Mediterranean environment);
- **Med-CORDEX** (Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment for the Mediterranean Region).

Both projects produced regional simulations covering the Mediterranean region under present climate and future scenarios. In particular, the regional coupled atmospheric-ocean models used in CIRCE simulated the A1B emission scenario, while the regional downscaling experiments available through the Med-CORDEX database simulate the rcp4.5 and rcp8.5 scenarios. In addition, two wave simulations have been forced directly with winds from the ECMWF reanalysis. The driving models for the Mediterranean wave simulations are listed in Table 2.

Table 2: regional forcing models used for the Mediterranean wave simulations

PROJECT	MODEL	HINDCAST	SCENARIO	ATMOS RESOLUTION
CIRCE	CMCC_LR		A1B 1951-2050	0.75°
	CMCC_HR		A1B 1951-2050	0.12°
	ENEA		A1B 1951-2050	30 km
	MPI		A1B 1951-2050	0.22°
	ARPEGE		A1B 1951-2050	50 Km in the Med region
	IPSL3		A1B 1951-2050	30 km
	IPSL2		A1B 1951-2050	30 km
Med-CORDEX	CNRM	1950-2005	Rcp4.5 2006-2100	50 km
			Rcp8.5 2006-2100	
	CMCC	1950-2005	Rcp4.5 2006-2100 Rcp8.5 1950-2100	50 km
	GUF	1950-2005	Rcp4.5 2006-2100 Rcp8.5 2006-2100	50 km
	LMD	1951-2005	Rcp4.5 2006-2100 Rcp8.5 2006-2100	50 km
	RCA4	1970-2000	Rcp8.5 2070-2099	
Reanalysis	COSMO- ERA11	1979-2013		
	HIPOCAS 1h / 6h	1958-2001		0.5°

Driving simulations for the HYPSE Surge Model (CMCC)

For the Mediterranean basin, an ensemble of simulations has been performed by CMCC, driven by atmospheric fields from the MEDCORDEX Database (listed in Table 3 below).

Table 3: regional forcing models used for Mediterranean surge simulations

Identifier of Model and Experiment	Period covered by the simulation
COSMO ERAINT011	1979-2013
ERAINT	1979-2013
COSMO ERAINT011-hypse-HR	1979-2013
CMCCrcp45	2005-2100
CMCCrcp85	1950-2100
CNRMrcp45	2006-2100
CNRMrcp85	1950-2100
GUrcp45	2006-2100
LMDrp45	2006-2100
LMDrp85	1951-2100
RCA4rcp85	1960-2100
GUrcp85	1950-2100
ITUclm	1970-2100
ITUbats	1970-2100

3.2 Wave modelling

The availability of reliable climatology and forecasts of wind-induced waves is crucial for the management of human activities at sea, the safety of coastal communities and the development of a variety of coastal and ocean engineering applications. In fact, short timescale applications also need to rely on the evaluation of wave climatology, independently of the main objective of the specific wave analysis or forecast. Even in operational wave forecasting, the comparison of results with wave climate (e.g. ranges and likelihood of height and period) and historical estimates of extremes is a valuable verification exercise for the output products, when observations are partial or lacking.

Ocean wave characteristics are mainly determined through field measurements, numerical simulation, physical models and analytical solutions, each method having its own advantages and disadvantages. Nowadays, however, numerical models emerge as one of the most powerful tools for the study of surface water waves

[Janssen, 2008]. They are based on the energy-balance equation and include the representation of the physical processes that are thought to control wave fields. The latter are sometimes not yet fully understood, and empirical results need to be used to varying degrees, allowing for a certain amount of tuning of the models and for differences among them. An introduction to wave modelling can be found in WMO, 1998.

The Coordinated Ocean Wave Climate Project (COWCLIP), an international collaborative research project and a component of the work-plan for the JCOMM Expert Team on Waves and Coastal Hazards, has, among its aims, the object of assessing the effects of climate variability and change on the wave climate. It produced numerous publications and datasets, that can be accessed through the project website at <https://cowclip.org/>. The global WavewatchIII (WWIII) simulations used for SOCLIMPACT all have the same model configuration and the same grid, extending in latitude from 80°S to 80°N at a spatial resolution of 1°. Output parameters have a 3-hourly temporal resolution. Historical data cover the period 1980-2005, while for the rcp8.5 scenario data are available over two twenty-year slices: mid-century (2026-2045) and end of the century (2080-2099) [Hemer and Trenham, 2016]. The driving global models are listed in Table 1.

A variety of studies have assessed the wave climate for specific sub-basins of the Mediterranean Sea, usually from the perspective of energy resource evaluation and therefore following a hindcast approach. The description of the only comprehensive climatological assessment of the Mediterranean wave climatology can be found in the dedicated section of this document (3.5.1).

Finally, several studies have been dedicated to the wave climate of the Baltic Sea [see, for example, Soomere and Räämet, 2011 and Groll et al., 2017], while a review of available data for the North Sea and the Baltic can be found at <https://www.coastdat.de/data/index.php.en>

3.3 Surge modelling

Storm surges are oscillations of the water level in a coastal or inland body of water in the time range of a few minutes to a few days, generated by atmospheric storm forcing, such as cyclones or developed mid-latitude lows, and represent one of the key topics in disaster risk reduction worldwide, despite their relatively infrequent occurrence. When a weather system moves over a water body, the atmospheric pressure gradient normal to the ocean surface cause water level to temporarily rise/fall by 1 centimeter per 1 hectopascal (hPa) reduction/increase at the center of the weather system. This phenomenon is referred to as the “inverse barometer effect” and represents the static part of the storm surge, usually representing a minor

contribution to the total magnitude. The second and dominant component of the storm surge, termed the dynamic amplification, is caused by the tangential wind stress (associated with the wind field of the weather system) acting over the ocean surface, which pushes the water towards the coast, thereby causing a pile-up of water at the coast. A brief treatment of the physics and modeling of storm surges can be found in the *Guide to Storm Surge Forecasting* issued by the World Meteorological Organization (WMO, 2011).

Several storm surge numerical models have been developed over the years, constantly improving as to both technical aspects (e.g. grid resolution or coordinates, model coupling) and representation of physical processes (Gonnert et al., 2001). However, surge modelling studies have often been focused on short time scales and occasional extreme events that caused severe damages to coastal areas, from the perspective of short term forecast and alert systems [Funakoshi et al., 2012; Ferrarin et al., 2013; Fernández-Montblanc et al., 2019]. Only recently more comprehensive analyses of such events have been reoriented to consider their occurrence on longer time scales and their correlation with large-scale drivers and tides [Bresson et al., 2018; Muis et al., 2019]. Following the line of a few initial studies [Debernard et al., 2003; Woth et al., 2006] the necessity to also account for climate change in approaching the subject has finally been widely recognized [Visser et al., 2014; Cid et al. 2016; Conte and Lionello, 2013; Forzieri et al., 2016; Vousdoukas et al., 2016; Vousdoukas et al., 2018a; Vousdoukas et al., 2018b]. In particular, Vousdoukas et al., 2016 contains an inventory of previous efforts to generate projections of extreme SSL under climate change scenarios and will produced a model-based database containing extreme storm surge levels (ESSL) at a European scale (also including most of Macaronesia and available at <http://data.jrc.ec.europa.eu/collection/LISCOAST>).

3.4 Deriving Sea Level estimates

The main processes that drive short-term (hours to days) changes in sea level are tides, surface waves, and storm surges. However, over longer periods, processes such as the thermal expansion of the ocean, continental ice melting or exchange of water with land reservoirs (e.g. snow, lakes, rivers, groundwater, artificial dams) must be considered, as well as their non-linear interactions with occasional transitory fluctuations, exceptional extreme events or irreversible alterations, either natural or anthropogenic. The effects of morphology, tectonics and geological uplifting or subsidence can also be locally relevant. The effective magnitude and relative weight of the concurring factors has a large geographical variation on multiple spatial scales. It is now clear that a wide variety of processes interact to determine seal level in too

complex a way to be accounted for by the mere superposition of anomalies over mean values.

As a matter of fact, the IPCC predicted a global average increase in sea level of about half meter by 2100 for all scenarios except RCP8.5 (for which the projection is of about one meter), caused by eustasy and thermal expansion [IPCC Report, 2014]. However, this value cannot be assumed to be representative of regional trends, because of changes in circulation, water masses, gravitational field, and vertical land movements. In the Mediterranean Sea several regional factors may contribute to a deviation from the global value. The hydraulic jumps observed in the Strait of Gibraltar and in the Bosphorus regulate inter-basin exchanges in a way that is still to be thoroughly assessed. Gibraltar constitutes the “choke” point that controls the transfer of global Relative Sea Level Rise from the north-east Atlantic into the Mediterranean, a mechanism that is still to be thoroughly understood and is in fact the object of on-going research. In addition, regional higher temperatures and evaporation rates also have an impact on local sea level, by changing seawater density patterns and determining the subsequent expansion/contraction of water columns (steric term) across the basin. The effects of Glacial Isostatic Adjustment (GIA) and geodetic variations is also still to be evaluated [Sannino, 2019].

As an exhaustive treatment of sea level rise is far beyond the scope of SOCLIMPACT, only the effects of waves and storm surges on sea level will be considered here, while the overall risk arising from the remaining terms will be qualitatively evaluated based on expert knowledge.

3.5 Analysis of different scenarios for the Mediterranean Sea

Extreme coastal flooding is often associated with winter low-pressure systems, which for Western Europe are mainly associated to mid-latitude cyclones that originate in the Atlantic Ocean. The amplification of wind-generated waves and surges by equinox tides within deep low-pressure systems can also produce a significant rise in sea level. Here we separately analyze future scenarios for the wave and the surge contributions to sea level rise, while the overall assessment of expected future sea level will be the object of D4.3 and D4.4b.

3.5.1 Waves

In the context of the Med-CORDEX programme, a comprehensive assessment of the Mediterranean wave climate under different scenarios has been initiated. Simulations have been performed by CMCC using the WAM model, at the horizontal resolution of $\frac{1}{4}^{\circ}$, driven by the regional models listed in Table 2.

In figures from 1 to 3, the seasonal means of Significant Wave Height (Hs) are presented for downscaled ERA-INTERIM and CMCC-driven simulations, averaged over

the historical and the future scenario reference periods (1982-2001 and 2080-2099), showing good agreement between the historical and hind cast simulations.

Figure 1a: ERAINT driven wave simulation- 1982-2001

Hs (m) mean DJF

Hs (m) mean MAM

Figure 1b: ERAINT driven wave simulation- 1982-2001

Hs (m) mean JJA

Hs (m) mean SON

Figure 2a: CMCC driven wave simulation- 1982-2001

Hs (m) mean DJF

Hs (m) mean MAM

Figure 2b: CMCC driven wave simulation- 1982-2001

Hs (m) mean JJA

Hs (m) mean SON

Figure 3a: CMCC driven wave simulation– RCP85 - 2080-2099

Hs (m) mean DJF

Hs (m) mean MAM

Figure 3b: CMCC driven wave simulation– RCP85 - 2080-2099

Hs (m) mean JJA

Hs (m) mean SON

3.5.2 Surge

A hydro-dynamical shallow water model (HYPSE, Hydrostatic Padua Sea Elevation model), driven by 6-hourly meteorological fields produced by different state-of-the-art global-regional climate model chains, has been used by CMCC to yield projections of storm surge fields in the Mediterranean basin, as induced by wind and atmospheric pressure. The contribution of tides can be switched on/off depending on the user needs. The model hindcast simulation (1958–2001) was validated against observed sea level (SL) values at 21 tide gauges [Conte D. and Lionello, P., 2013], its accuracy being crucially dependent on the quality of the atmospheric forcing. The climate change signal was demonstrated to be especially sensitive to the choice of the global model that drives the regional simulation. The choice of the regional climate model and the resolution of the hydro-dynamical model represent secondary sources of uncertainty. Analysis of the ensemble of simulations reveals a modest (about –5%), although clear and widespread decrease in the amplitude of both positive and negative large storm surges along the coast of the Mediterranean Sea.

The HYPSE model has been recently forced with atmospheric fields from an ensemble of regional coupled simulations to project surges in the Mediterranean Sea. The driving atmospheric fields are available from the MEDCORDEX database (see section 3.1.2 above). The Gumbel extreme value analysis was applied to two sample simulations only differing as to the regional driving model. Results for the CMCC driven historical simulation are presented in Figures 4 and 5, where Return Level maps are presented for Return Times of 40 and 10 years, respectively. Results for the CMCC driven RCP85 simulation are shown in Figures 6 and 7, while the corresponding results for the CNRM driven historical and RCP85 simulations are shown in Figures from 8 to 11.

**Figure 4 : Return Levels for $Q_t = 40$ years
CMCC - 1986-2005**

**Figure 5 : Return Levels for $Q_t = 10$ years
CMCC - 1986-2005**

Figure 6: RCP85 - Return levels for $Q_t = 40$ years
CMCC - 2081-2100

**Figure 7: RCP85 - Return levels for $Q_t = 10$ years
CMCC - 2081-2100**

**Figure 8: Return Levels for $Q_t = 40$ years
CNRM - 1986-2005**

**Figure 9: Return Levels for $Q_t = 10$ years
CNRM - 1986-2005**

**Figure 10: RCP85 - Return Levels for $Q_t = 40$ years
CNRM - 2081-2100**

**Figure 11: RCP85 - Return Levels for $Q_t = 10$ years
CNRM - 2081-2100**

The pattern of expected return levels clearly reveals how the tidal contribution dominates over wind and pressure induced storm surge for both models (Figure 12 shows the M2 component pattern) and confirms the already mentioned moderate decrease in surge amplitude for the Mediterranean. However, local sea level being the results of a variety of interacting processes over a wide range of spatial and time scales, these results do not rule out the hypothesis of significantly increased sea-level-related coastal hazards. The latter may well be augmented by rising mean sea level or by land subsidence and tectonics, counteracting the likely attenuation of storminess predicted by the HYPSE simulations, which only represents the high frequency contribution to the overall SL. In fact, Lionello et al. 2017 have shown that even a moderate sea level rise will overcompensate for the decrease of wave height and storm surge maxima, producing an increase in hazard levels along the continental coast of the Mediterranean Sea. SOCLIMPACT will provide the opportunity to evaluate the future hazard level also for the Mediterranean Islands.

Figure 12: Amplitude (in m) of M2 tidal component derived from the model

4. SOCLIMPACT new simulations

4.1 Motivation

From the analysis of data available over the areas of interest for SOCLIMPACT, an evident lack of high-resolution wave simulations comprising the Atlantic islands (West Indies, and Macaronesia) emerged. For this reason, new dedicated simulations have been performed by ENEA using the WaveWatchIII model (WW3), for three Atlantic domains including the Antilles, the Canaries, the Azores and Madeira.

In order to reach sufficient resolution, three levels of nesting have been implemented:

- a low-resolution experiment, with a grid covering the entire Atlantic Ocean at the spatial resolution of 1°;
- an intermediate resolution experiment, with a grid extending from 10°N to 42°N at the spatial resolution of 0.25°;
- three high resolution experiments, with smaller grids at the resolution of 0.05°.
- Figure. 13 shows the grids employed for these additional wave simulations.

Figure 13: extension of the nested domains for the new wave simulations

4.2

Analysis of new data

4.2.1 Comparison with observations and past simulations

The ECMWF ERA5 reanalysis were taken as reference to validate the new wave simulations. ERA5 data are produced with a coupled ocean-atmosphere-wave global model, whose wave component is the ECMWF-WAM model, at a spatial resolution of 0.36°

A test simulation for year 1997 was performed in order to check the model setup, using surface winds from ERA5 as forcing. Significant wave heights computed by the model at 0.25° resolution were compared to the corresponding results from the ERA5 reanalysis. Scatter plots in two points close to the nested areas are presented in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Scatter plots of 3-hourly significant wave heights for year 1997 computed using the 0.25° WW3 vs ERA5 data

Very few buoy data are available in the areas of interest. Here we show the results of a preliminary comparison with the NOAA-42060 buoy, located close to the Antilles, at 63.35°W, 16.41°N. Scatter plots for the intermediate and the high-resolution models are shown in Figure. 15.

Figure 15: Scatter plots showing 3-hourly significant wave heights for year 1997 from the 0.25° WW3 model (left panel) and from the 0.05° WW3 model (right panel) vs observations recorded at 63.35°W, 16.41°N

The new WW3 high-resolution simulations have been performed using 3-hourly surface winds derived from the HadGEM global model under the rcp8.5 scenario. A preliminary sample comparison of mean significant wave heights between the new and the global low-resolution simulations for the area including the Canary Islands is shown in figures from 16 to 19, for the periods 1996-2005 and 2090-2099. Results show an overall agreement as to large-scale patterns, as well as the dramatic effect of resolution on small-scale features.

Figure 16: Significant wave height seasonal means from the global HadGEM2-ES simulation over the Canary Islands for the period 1996-2005.

Figure 17: Significant wave height seasonal means from the global HadGEM2-ES simulation over the Canary Islands for the period 2090-2099 under the rcp8.5 scenario.

Figure 18: Significant wave height seasonal means derived from the WW3 high resolution simulation for the Canary Islands for the period 1996-2005.

Figure 19: Significant wave height seasonal means derived from the WW3 high resolution simulation for the Canary Islands for the period 2090-2099 under the rcp8.5 scenario

4.2.2 Necessity and feasibility of bias-correction

Due to its relative simplicity and low computational cost and to the increasing demand for high resolution unbiased input data to feed impact models, bias correction has become a popular practice among climate modellers, prompting the development of a variety of methods and applications [Teutschbein and Seibert, 2012; Hempel et al., 2013; Harding et al., 2014].

As a matter of fact, despite their invaluable contribution to our understanding of climate change, models are usually biased and their resolution is often too low for reliable impact assessments. Many users of model data therefore apply some form of bias correction to model output, aiming to adjust the statistics of climate projections to those observed over a present-day reference period. However, bias-correction validation is often based on marginal aspects and should be complemented by further analyses. Current methods do not modify the climate change signal in a physically grounded way, although they are usually trend-preserving, nor can they generate information on sub-grid processes that are not explicitly resolved by the original model. For a critical review of bias correction methods, see Vannitsem, 2011; Maraun, 2013; Maraun, 2016, Maraun et al., 2017.

As regards wave and surge modelling, the implementation of bias correction is further complicated by the lack of extensive, distributed observations over long periods. It might be feasible to apply corrections to better match local time series in selected locations, depending on users' needs and data availability, in case of critical deviations between models and observations, keeping in mind all the caveats in using such a practice.

5. Conclusions

The main practical scope of the review conducted for this report was to assess data gaps that might condition the computation of meaningful wave and surge related hazard indicators and the subsequent activities of SOCLIMPACT.

From our survey, we can conclude that:

- the Mediterranean region is sufficiently covered by already available wave and surge data;
- climatological datasets describing surges in the Atlantic Ocean, and specifically for the islands selected for the project, are generally lacking; however, qualitative evaluation of surge relative contribution to sea level can be inferred from the cited literature;
- available wave climatology over the Atlantic Ocean has too low a resolution to be of any use for the scope of the project; we therefore decided to perform new dedicated simulations, whose preliminary results are very satisfactory and indicate that bias correction of projections is probably unnecessary;
- surge and wave data for the north coast of Europe and the Baltic Islands are available from EU portals.

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